

New Education Policy-2020: Opportunities & Challenges

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Abstract

Because education promotes social and economic advancement, a nation's school and college systems must have a clear, futuristic education strategy. For it to be effective, several nations use respective educational systems that consider culture and tradition and adopt distinct phases throughout their life cycles. India's new educational system is envisioned under the NEP-2020 (National Education Policy 2020), which the Indian Union Cabinet adopted on July 29, 2020. The old policy, the NEP-1986, has been replaced. The strategy provides a comprehensive framework for education from early childhood to higher education and skills courses in rural and urban areas. By 2021, the policy intends to have changed the education system in India. A short time after the programme was announced, the government clarified that no one would be required to study a particular language and that English would not replace other regional languages as the teaching language.

Key words: Government, Higher Education, NEP-2020, Education, Challenges, Opportunities.

Introduction

India, a nation that is becoming more amenable to educational changes, now has 845 universities and roughly forty thousand HIEs, showing the country's high degree of fragmentation and a large number of smaller HEIs that are connected to these universities. Over 40% of these small institutions are running a single programme, which goes against the anticipated transition to a diversified higher education, which is a crucial necessity for the education systems in the nation for the twenty-first century. In addition, it should be noted that more than 20% of colleges have annual enrolments of less than 100 students, making it impossible for them to enhance the quality of education, and only 4% of colleges enroll more than 3,000 students annually because of regional imbalance and the caliber of education they provide.

By 2030-2022, India's GDP is expected to reach 10 trillion dollars, making it the third-largest economy in the world. Knowledge resources rather than the nation's natural resources will power the 10 trillion dollar economy. Therefore, the present government opted to overhaul the Indian education system by announcing a unified Education Policy 2020 to foster the sector's growth. The Prime Minister recently urged using the 4th Industrial Revolution to propel India to new heights, which is in accordance with his statement. In order to develop our country sustainably into a just and thriving knowledge society, the recently proposed NEP-2020 envisioned an education system focused on India that offers quality education to everyone. The NEP-2020 was introduced in Himachal Pradesh. By 2022, the Indian school system should have adopted the national educational policy.

Methodology

This paper is based on secondary data, collected from journals and websites.

About New Education Policy

The NEP was first framed in 1986 and then revised in 1992. During this time, our nation has undergone several changes, including those to the economy, society, and the world. As a result, the education sector must be improved or changed to meet the needs of the people, the community, and

the nation in the 21st century. Innovation and research of the finest quality will be the cornerstones on which India will become a knowledge superpower. Therefore, the government started developing a new educational policy through a consultation process to take an inclusive, participative, and all-encompassing approach.

New NEP-2020 was developed through an unprecedented round of consultation that included input from 2.5 lakh Panchayats, 6600 Blocks, 6000 ULBs, and 676 Districts. This policy involved around 2 lakh proposals. Beginning in January 2015, the MHRD started an unprecedented consultation process that was comprehensive, collaborative, and highly participative. Under the leadership of the late Shri T.S.R. Subramanian, a former cabinet secretary, the "Committee for Formulation of the NEP" released its report in May 2016. Based on this research, the Ministry has provided some inputs for the 2016 Draft National Education Policy.

A "Committee for the Draft NEP" was constituted in June 2017 and presided over by renowned scientist Dr. K. Kasturirangan. HRD Minister received the draught NEP on May 31, 2019. It was uploaded on the MHRD website and at the "My Gov Innovate" portal for comments and recommendations from stakeholders, including the general public.

New National Education Policy 2020: Facts at a Glance

School Education: Facts

With a 100% Gross Enrollment Ratio (GER) in school education by 2030, the new policy aims to make education accessible to all children from preschool to secondary level.

- The NEP 2020 will reintegrate two crores of out-of-school children into the open schooling system.
- A new 5+3+3+4 curricular structure will replace the school's current 10+2 system, corresponding to ages 3-8, 8-11, 11-14, and 14-18, respectively. In addition, under the school curriculum, this new system will bring an uncovered age group of 3 to 6 years. This age has gained widespread recognition as the critical period in a child's development of their mental skills.
- According to the new policy, there will be 12 years of formal schooling followed by three years of Anganwadi/preschool.
- The new policy focuses on fundamental literacy and numeracy skills. Schools will not have a rigid division between academic, extracurricular, and vocational streams. Internships would be the first step in vocational education, starting in class 6.
- According to the New Education Policy, teaching will be provided in students' native or regional language up to at least Grade 5. No student will be forced to learn a language.
- To achieve learning outcomes, students' progress will be monitored in conjunction with assessment reforms via a Holistic Progress Card (360-degree).
- The NCTE, in cooperation with the NCERT, will develop a new and exhaustive National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education (NCFTE 2021). By 2030, the minimum degree requirement for teaching will be a 4-year integrated B.Ed.

Higher Education: Facts

- In higher education, the Gross Enrollment Ratio will be increased to 50 per cent by 2035, and 3.5 crore seats will be added. Subjects in higher education curricula must be flexible.
- Several entries and exits will be permitted with the appropriate documentation. In addition, to facilitate the Transfer of Credits, the Academic Bank of Credits will be created.
- National Research Foundation will be formed as the apex organisation for developing robust research culture and expanding research capability across higher education.
- The Higher Education Commission of India (HECI) would be formed for all higher education, except for medical and legal education. It will be a single umbrella organisation.
- The Higher Education Commission of India (HECI) will have four autonomous divisions: National Higher Education Regulatory Council (NHERC) for regulation, General Education

Council (GEC) for standard-setting, and Higher Education Grants Council (HEGC) for funding, and National Accreditation Council (NAC) for accreditation.

- The Affiliation System will be phased out over the next fifteen years, and colleges will be granted varying degrees of autonomy.

Challenges of NEP-2020

In India, there are approximately one thousand universities. As one of the policies has declared aims, doubling the Gross Enrollment Ratio in higher education by 2035 will need the opening of one new university per week for the next fifteen years. Unquestionably, opening a new university every week is a daunting task. National Education Policy 2020 aims to re-enrol two crores of out-of-school children. Over 15 years, it will be necessary to establish approximately 50 schools per week in order to achieve this goal.

From a financing perspective, this is not a task for the faint of heart. The National Education Policy 2020 foresees an increase in education budgets from 4.6% to 6% of GDP, or over INR 2.5 lakh crores annually. This funding will be well-spent on the construction of schools and universities around the nation, the hiring of teachers and professors, and operational expenses such as delivering complimentary breakfast to schoolchildren. Despite the strain on the exchequer, economists have advocated for stimulus packages comprising double-digit percentages of GDP.

The policy calls for a significant structural overhaul of the curriculum in education, which is a move that should be applauded. However, to offer this curriculum properly, we want teachers who have received pedagogical training and are aware of the requirements. In addition, parents and instructors must make significant mental adjustments to implement many of the curriculum modifications. The National Education Policy 2020's emphasis on inter-disciplinary learning is a welcome development for higher education. For many years, universities, particularly those in India, have been highly compartmentalised and siloed. The National Education Policy 2020 includes some measures to enhance the standard and breadth of the Indian educational system.

Opportunities of NEP 2020

The unfinished agenda of NEP – 1986 is where the New Education Policy starts. The roots of NEP – 1986 were found in a completely different India. In access and equity, notable advancements have been made over time. It has been possible to reach nearly universal primary enrollment levels and the rise in higher education enrollment (GER: 26.3 per cent). However, a decline in the standard of instruction in public education systems has also occurred, followed by a flight of upper- and middle-class residents. Additionally, accountability systems were weaker as a result of this. Public system compensation structures have gradually increased despite low returns on learning.

Higher Education

Considering the strategy in light of current events at public universities and the recent scandal at prestigious universities is critical. The state has been steadily eroding universities' independence. The best public university in India targeted perverse governmental violence that did not just happen in the past. At best, there are political appointments of university administrators who serve as the state's tools rather than those primarily concerned with teaching, learning, research, or administration. The text emphasises regulatory autonomy, but it would be concerning if it also implied financial autonomy.

- The UGC (University Grants Commission) and AICTE (All India Council for Technical Education) would be replaced to achieve this "imagined" autonomy. The Higher Education Commission of India is a new organisation based on function and activity separation.
- The policy also opposes the commercialization of education. The same measure does, however, allow foreign universities to visit India. In addition, private institutions operated by Indian suppliers have significantly increased in number. It would make sense if the intention were to boost competition. The statement's insertion, however, does not.

- It makes sense to focus on a futuristic curriculum, and creating a distinct organisation to address technological integration in institutions is a critical step in that direction.
- Indian universities will be able to open campuses around the globe; the gulf markets hold a lot of potential for this to happen. Indians living abroad have a great need for high-quality education.

Criticism of NEP 2020

Below is a list of complaints against NEP 2020 that have been made or may be made.

- First, the NEP avoided parliamentary discussion, control, and examination. This somewhat rushed approach appears to be intended to make a political point because it was introduced during a period when parliament was not in session because of COVID-19. However, the incident has also occurred previously. Over the past six years, it has been common practice to exclude members of parliament from essential debates, preventing them from critically analysing policies, expressing their opinions, and making amendment suggestions.
- The policy is a visionary document that leaves out the lowest socioeconomic groups and offers little to no relief to the underprivileged, women, and caste and religious minorities while glossing over essential issues with access to education that has long been an issue. Moreover, there is no detailed roadmap or well-thought-out implementation plan to carry out this lofty goal.
- This plan's execution requires many undefined milestones and a financial commitment. Consider the statement, "The Centre and the States will work together to raise the public investment in the Education sector to achieve 6 per cent of GDP at the earliest," for instance. The government cannot be held responsible without a clear promise.
- Three Language formula: Although the policy does not require this provision, it is written in a way that limits the options and flexibility available to the students, instructors, and schools. Additionally, it is blatantly against a Supreme Court ruling. The way this is written is sure to remind people of the anti-Hindi struggle of 1965, which was against the federal government's goal to make Hindi an official language. Political groups in the South believe that the Modi administration is attempting to impose Hindi in nations that do not speak it. This is true notwithstanding the centre's clarification that it will not impose any language on any state and that the state itself will make the final choice.
- The RTE Act is not included in the NEP 2020; therefore, universal education cannot be implemented without legislative support. The RTE is not connected to elementary and secondary education in any way. Legally, the centre/state is not bound by this. The RTE forum noted that the final policy "talks about the universalization of school education from 3-18 years, without making it a legal right. Therefore, the union and state governments are not required to implement a mechanism to make it a reality. Universalization will be exceedingly challenging without the RTE Act.

Conclusion

Higher education has a significant role in determining the economy, social standing, adoption of new technologies, and healthy human behaviour in any nation. Therefore, the country's education department must enhance GER so that all citizens can take advantage of higher education opportunities. The National Education Policy of India 2020 is working toward achieving this goal by implementing creative policies to raise the standard, make it more appealing, make it more affordable, and increase the supply of higher education by opening up the sector to the private sector while also enforcing stringent quality standards in all higher education institutions. NEP-2020 is anticipated to achieve its goals by 2030 by promoting merit-based admissions with free ships and scholarships, merit-based proven leaders in governing bodies, merit-based continuous performers as faculty members, and strict quality monitoring through biennial accreditation based on self-declaration of progress through technology-based monitoring.

All institutes of higher education will evolve into multidisciplinary autonomous colleges with the ability to grant degrees in their name or become constituent colleges of their affiliated universities. Innovative projects in the basic sciences applied sciences, and social sciences & humanities will get funding from the National Research Foundation, an unbiased organisation. With the option to select core and allied subjects inside and across disciplines, the higher education system will be student-centred. Additionally, within the boundaries of the established policy framework, faculty members are free to select their curricula, methodologies, pedagogies, and evaluation methods. Beginning with the academic year 2021-2022, these changes will last until 2030, when it is anticipated that the first stage of the changes will become apparent.

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